

ECOBULK

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

GA NUMBER: 730456

Legal and Regulatory, Environmental and H&S Requirements

Document Information

Report name	Legal and Regulatory, Environmental and H&S Requirements
Version number	2.0
Document number	D7.6
Due date for deliverable	31/08/2021
Actual submission date	30/11/2021
Lead beneficiary	ITENE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 730456

Document Control page

Authors	Sergio Güerri
Version number	1.0
Date	25/11/2021
Modified by	-
Comments	
Status	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Draft <input type="checkbox"/> Accepted
Action requested	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> To be revised Deadline for action:

Revision History

Version	Date	Author/Reviewer	Notes
1.0	09/09/2021	Sergio Güerri	Business models requirements
2.0	30/11/2021	Sergio Güerri	Completed

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Executive Summary

After analysing the current legislation and regulations on the process of recovery, recycling and reuse of parts, elements and materials of products from the sectors under study, the next step is to identify those initiatives within this framework that promote and/or strengthen the design of circular models.

To this end, the first part of this document deals with a study of the different business models defined in the project, with the aim of identifying the main barriers that currently exist in terms of policies, so as to define actions, mainly related to regulatory and fiscal frameworks, to mitigate them and, therefore, to promote these new circular models.

In order to complete the previous study, from the result of the different demo cases developed, the requirements coming from the different agents involved in the value chain are analysed, leading to potential initiatives to be carried out in the mentioned frameworks.

1. Introduction

Prior to this, an analysis was carried out of the existing legislation linked to activities involving the recovery, recycling, treatment and reincorporation of parts and/or complete elements from the automotive, furniture and construction (external furniture) sectors, at the end of their life. This legislation addresses aspects that guarantee the technical properties of the element, as well as health and safety, both in the reverse logistics processes (from collection to re-manufacturing) and from the user's point of view.

The definition and design of new circular models in the framework of the three sectors analysed has made it possible to identify the main barriers, in different areas, that hinder their implementation and deployment. Two of these areas is legislative and regulatory, and fiscal. In this context, and based on the previous analysis, the first part of this study aims to establish possible initiatives in the regulatory framework that facilitate the development of the business models define.

Simultaneously, during the project, different demonstrators have been developed, associated with different business models, from which it has been possible to obtain interesting results, including, among others, possible needs in terms of legislation, to facilitate their deployment. It is precisely these needs that allow the definition of initiatives that could be included in the policies to be developed.

2. Overview of current legislation on circular economy deployment

Referring to the institutional environment, laws and regulations affecting circular economy have focused mostly on the topics related to waste management¹ and have aimed mainly to enhance safe waste management through the sorting of waste, landfill diversion, charges and taxes and extended producer responsibility (EPR). The EU Circular Action Plan (European Commission, 2015) is an evolution of these policies as it proposes policy interventions across the life cycle of products that should be considered in the short/medium term of policy development². policies address different levels of the implementation of CE affecting industry, society, and governments

The following table shows the different National strategies and legislations for promotion of circular economy in Europe. Source: Circular Economy Platform (<https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform>), Ecopreneur.eu (2019), countries websites

Country	Year	Title, Type of Document and Reach
Germany	2012	Act to Promote Circular Economy and Safeguard the Environmentally Compatible Management of Waste (Legislative Act, National)
	2016	National Programme of sustainable consumption: From Sustainable Lifestyles towards Social Change (Framework program, National)
	2019	German Packaging Act (Legislative Act, National)
	2016	Resource Efficiency Program Phase II (Framework program)
Belgium	2016	Regional Program in Circular Economy 2016-2020 Mobilizing resources and minimizing lost wealth: for an innovative regional economy (Program)
	2017	Circular Flanders Kick-off Statement (Report, Flanders Region)
Denmark	2018	Strategy for Circular Economy: More value and better environment through design, consumption, and recycling (Strategy, National)
	2017	The Advisory Board for Circular Economy - Recommendations for the Danish Government (Guidelines, National)
	2017	Circular Economy - Denmark as Circular Economy Solution HUB (Guidelines, National)

¹ Winans, Kendall and Deng, 2017; Berg et al., 2018; Nylén and Salminen, 2019

² Milios, 2018

Spain	2018	Extremadura 2030 – Green and Circular Economy Strategy (Action plan)
	2015	Promoting the Green Economy and the Circular Economy – Competitiveness, Efficiency, Innovation (Act, Cataluña Region)
	2019	Circular Economy and Waste Management in the Basque Country (Action plan, Basque Country)
Finland	2016	Leading the cycle Finnish road map to a circular economy 2016–2025 (Roadmap, National)
	2019	Finland’s Road Map to Circular Economy 2.0 (Roadmap, National)
	2017	Regional road map towards circular economy in Päijät-Häme (Roadmap, regional)
	2019	Riihimäki’s circular economy roadmap (Roadmap, local)
France	2018	Circular Economy roadmap of France: 50 measures for a 100% circular economy (Guidelines, National)
	2017	Paris Circular Economy Plan (Roadmap, local)
The Netherlands	2016	A Circular Economy in the Netherlands by 2050 - Government-wide Programme for a Circular Economy (Roadmap, National)
Ireland	2017	Moving Towards a Circular Economy in Ireland (Report, National)
Italy	2017	Towards a Model of Circular Economy for Italy - Overview and strategic framework (Guidelines, National)
Portugal	2017	Leading the transition [Action plan for circular economy in Portugal: 2017-2020] (Roadmap, National)
Greece	2018	National Action Plan on Circular Economy (Roadmap, National)
Luxembourg	2018	National Waste and Resource Management Plan (Roadmap, National)
Slovenia	2018	Roadmap towards the Circular Economy in Slovenia (Roadmap, National)
	2018	Strategy for the Transition to Circular Economy in the Municipality of Maribor (Strategy, local)
Slovak Republic		Slovak Republic goes green economy (Roadmap, National)
Malta	2018	Malta’s Sustainable Development Vision for 2050

Furthermore, incentives are often presented as opportunities related to solving barriers for implementation of circular economy, either systemic in nature or sector-specific (e.g., ICT). Although no operationalization for the implementation of policies were presented, Whalen, Milios and Nussholz (2018) suggest examples of policy initiatives that can support circular economy. They are:

- Take-back incentives
- Monetary incentives
- Mechanisms to reduction of labour costs (lowering labour taxes)
- Legislative, legal and regulatory frameworks
- Extended Producer Responsibility
- Tax incentives
- Legal waste definitions affecting product end-of-life

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- Skills development (training and educational activities) - e.g., training for refurbishers
 - [Obligations to] provide spare parts
 - [Obligations to] provide product information to repairers, refurbishers, remanufacturers
 - Enforcement of longer warranty periods for consumers
 - Support to innovative, circular economy-focused business models
 - Development of infrastructure for consumers to hand in used products
 - Introduction of material efficiency and durability in product design regulation
 - Legal framework to facilitate trade of repaired and refurbished goods
 - Reduction of value-added tax (VAT) for refurbished products
 - Creation of subsidies for reuse that could help reduce operational costs and assist reuse operations

All these incentives they were categorized in the following main categories: technological, educational, social, regulatory, institutional, market conditions, fiscal, and industrial arrangements. This study will identify some of the main incentives relating mainly to **regulatory and fiscal** frameworks. In the analysis also the nature of incentives has been considered: positive and negative, being an example of the first one the pricing reduction for secondary products; and, for the second, penalties for not adequate waste collection and charges and restrictions for the landfilling and incineration of waste.

As indicated throughout the project, a framework should be designed to enable the intrinsic value of materials to be preserved or enhanced along production systems and value chains and to minimise at the same time the level of inputs of virgin materials. According to the European Commission Expert Group on Circular Economy Financing, the following principles need to be taken into account when formulating policy interventions:

- Value preservation and creation
- Proportionality (to the level of externality)
- Progressive dematerialisation
- Sensitivity to innovation
- Additionality, which is the need to ensure that new policy interventions integrate with and support the effective and timely implementation of existing related policies or enhance their impact.

Additionally, at the national level, Great Britain is the only European country who created a cross-sectoral standard for differentiating remanufacturing with the BS 8887-2:2009 Design

for manufacture, assembly, disassembly and end-of-life processing (MADE). In the aerospace industry, the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) is certifying the companies able to proceed remanufacturing of aircraft parts. In the automotive sector, private remanufacturers associations are active promoters in Europe, such as the Automotive Parts Remanufacturers Association, but do not carry their own quality certifications standards. In Germany, however, the German Association of the Automotive Industry (VDA) for automotive parts established the VDA 6.1 standard. The Consumer Protection Law enforces a warranty period of 1 year.

3. Business models analysis

Aligned with the analysis of the different circular business models defined in the project (WP8), and more specifically those associated with the different demo cases that have been carried out in the project, for each of the three sectors under study: automotive, furniture and construction.

3.1 Restraints/gaps for the three sectors

The main barriers and/or complexities that hinder the establishment of the business models studied in WP8, for each of the three sectors analysed, are shown below. These barriers are distributed in the following groups:

- Technical
- Market
- Information
- Policy and legal

As a result of this analysis, a series of regulatory proposals will be defined to minimise these barriers.

- **Automotive sector**

The new chain associated with the recovery and valorisation of end-of-life elements in the automotive sector faces the following constraints

Barrier type	Barrier description
Technical barriers	Surface finishing and embedding of accessories into plastic component parts limits the recyclability of composite and plastic component parts

	Due to current technical limits on the separation of plastics from automotive shredder residue (ASR), this limits the recovery and recycling of most internal automotive plastic component parts.
Market barriers	The cost (primarily labour) makes vehicle disassembly into individual component parts economically un-viable.
Information barriers	Without adequate monitoring of automotive components, delivering product life extension becomes less cost and resource efficient.
Policy and legal barriers	Plastic, including plastic-based composites do not have a clear path to recovery or recycling
	OEMs currently fulfil the end-of-life vehicles directive without the need to increase automotive plastic recycling

- **Furniture sector**

Similar to the automotive sector, the furniture sector presents the following barriers to the establishment of the leasing model defined in ECOBULK, with the aim of extending product life from 10 to 20 years through a repair service:

Barrier type	Barrier description
Technical barriers	A lack of harmonized standards across Europe for waste wood classifications limits the volumes of waste particle board available.
Market barriers	Supply of waste wood back to the particle board sector is influenced by better prices paid within other markets (such as biobased energy providers)
	The costs of innovation (for example for changes required to other functions within a business) are prohibitive for SMEs
	Public procurement of furniture is not based on circular principles, missing an opportunity to support innovation in circular economy business models.
Information barriers	Consumers (including business customers within the value chain) may consider a product using recycled wood to be of a lower quality than virgin wood

Policy and legal barriers	A lack of policies that support the cascading of particle board and other wood products results in the majority of waste wood being incinerated as biomass for energy production or landfilled
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- **Construction sector**

Following the analysis of the different business models defined in ECOBULK for this sector, the following barriers have been identified:

Barrier type	Barrier description
Technical barriers	Lack of expertise/training for using rLFT pellets/waste GFRP particles limits experimentation and uptake Lack of standards and certification for the recycled composites with rGFRP
Market barriers	Waste owners will not pay additional costs for recycling when alternative waste disposal routes exist Uncertainty in the business case/revenues and end markets for recycling solutions limits the potential for investment Competitive market for products – some already with recycled plastic/wood credentials - could limit uptake of products (especially due to potentially unknown material content)
Information barriers	Lack of information regarding the composition of feedstock when sources are variable and unknown (as might be typical from post-consumer products). Benefits of recycling composites are not clear or widely known
Policy and legal barriers	Alternative, non-circular waste disposal routes are available and cheaper for composites Composite companies and others in the value chain currently have no obligations to recover and recycle materials

3.2 Legislation initiatives in circular economy

This section identifies several policy initiatives and/or action to be addressed, which are of great interest to remove the above-mentioned barriers in the different sectors. Specifically, for each of these initiatives, as far as possible, a timescale for their development (short, medium, or long term) is established.

- **Automotive sector**

Initiative /Action	Timescale
➤ The sector should establish a clear vision regarding plastics and composite material recovery and recycling	Short term
➤ Stakeholder groups need to be established to facilitated collaboration and action to improve recovery and recycling of post use automotive plastics	Short term
➤ Legal requirements (such as landfill bans or requirements to recover and recycle plastics) or fiscal incentives (such as taxing non recycled plastics) would provide the stimuli needed for engagement at scale with plastic component recovery, establishing a market for high quality secondary plastic	Short - Medium term

- **Furniture sector**

Initiative /Action	Timescale
➤ Establishment of wood waste collection systems that promote its reuse, beyond the current widespread collection to landfill services	Short term
➤ Develop waste policies and incentives that support the reuse of wood fibers, in particular before incineration even for energy production	Short- Medium term
➤ Consider landfill bans or higher disposal taxes for waste particle board to encourage recovery and reused	Medium term

➤ Deployment of Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) systems as a powerful tool for promoting effective waste management solutions	Short-Medium term

• **Construction sector**

Initiative /Action	Timescale
➤ Making alternative disposal routes less economically favorable (e.g., through raising gate fees) or banning disposal options (e.g., as with Germany's landfill ban for composites) would favor recycling solutions	Short term
➤ Clearly differentiate the cement kiln co-processing route which is not recycling in the EU-legislation and waste statistics	Short term
➤ Implementing an EPR scheme would channel resources into reprocessing operations	Short term
➤ In the wind energy sector require the applicant seeking a new permit for a new wind turbine to recycle the turbine blades at EoL in a sustainable way – as well as take care of recycling all the old blades included in the given permits of the same applicant	Short term
➤ Need for labelling for composite materials, to facilitate their retrieval	Medium term
➤ Tightening of regulations on the recovery and recycling of GFRP waste	Sort-Medium term

4. Pilot case analysis

In this section, the aim is to identify possible initiatives in terms of regulations and legislation that promote circular models, because of the experiences obtained in the demonstrators developed in the project, and the vision of the different partners/stakeholders involved.

As mentioned in the first section, these initiatives will focus on regulatory and fiscal aspects.

4.1 Regulatory incentives

In the regulatory field, two main actions, including ecodesign, waste and extended producer responsibility stand out with a view to fostering the development of circular models among industry sectors:

- **Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR)** as a set of instruments to be implemented through administrative, economic, and informative policy instruments³. In EPR, the producer's responsibility for a product is extended to after the use stage of a product's life cycle.

Enhanced EPR measures could help to improve EPR schemes in three main ways:

- Improving the implementation of legislation (e.g. to attain existing and new, more ambitious, waste targets), and the integration of EPR into environmental and circular economy objectives (e.g. through wider application of EPR to other products). This would contribute to reducing the environmental externalities of packaging waste
- Strengthening the financial incentives for eco-design. Economic incentives should be developed to favour circular products and business models (e.g. through harmonised criteria and the further application of modulated fees to support the waste hierarchy and incentivise more environmentally sustainable products).
- Enhancing the market performance of existing schemes. This could be done by: developing clearer definitions at the EU level to support harmonised approaches; ensuring clear allocation of responsibilities between stakeholders; ensuring maximum cost coverage; facilitating fair competition; and ensuring transparency on schemes' performance and costs
- EPR has the unique potential to foster innovation in circular design for all companies by applying eco-modulation of fees to give a positive economic incentive

In France, the principle of extended producer responsibility has been enshrined in law since 1975. The first nationwide system was introduced in 1992 for the collection of packaging waste from private final consumers. Later, similar systems were introduced for batteries and accumulators, paper, electrical and electronic equipment, etc. Meanwhile there are about 20 different EPR systems ("channels") in France.

³ Rezero (Mitjans Sanz et al., 2017)

With the new Recycling Management Act, primarily European requirements were implemented. In addition to a variety of other measures, the law provides for the creation of ten new EPR channels and the expansion of the scope of some existing channels. This affects in particular toys, cigarettes, sanitary textiles, building products and materials, motor vehicles, etc.

Following the reform, article L.541-10-1 of the Environmental Code provides for extended producer responsibility for the following products (among others):

- building products and building materials (from 1.1.2022),
 - electrical and electronic equipment,
 - batteries and accumulators,
 - chemical products and their containers which may pose a significant risk to health and the environment in so far as they constitute household waste (as from 1.1.2021 all waste of these products),
 - furniture and upholstered seating or sleeping furniture (from 1.1.2022 also textile decorative elements),
 - passenger cars, vans, two- or three-wheeled motor vehicles and four-wheeled motor vehicles (from 1.1.2022),
 - tyres (from 1.1.2023),
 - mineral or synthetic lubricating or industrial oils (from 1.1.2022),
- **Ecodesign:** the goal is to include aspects such as durability, reparability, upgradeability, disassembly, information and ease of reuse and recycling, greenhouse gas and other emissions in the design phase of products. A large part of this initiative has been addressed in the Ecodesign Working Plan 2016-2019⁴.

In this framework the following tables shows the main requirements of the different actors in the sectors analysed:

Sector	Regulatory incentives/actions
	Regulate consumption with environmental standards and not just local production so as not to give a cost advantage to developing countries that do not apply the same environmental and worker protection standards in their manufacturing processes, together with greater market surveillance to combat unfair competition

⁴ European Commission, 2016

Automotive	Promote <i>ecodesign</i> in the phases prior to product development to facilitate disassembly, establishing coding standards and reverse logistics to improve the flow of recycled materials for remanufacturing
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Sector	Regulatory incentives/actions
Furniture	Legislation to make the "polluter pays" principle a reality
	Promote <i>ecodesign</i> in the phases prior to product development to facilitate disassembly, establishing coding standards and reverse logistics to improve the flow of recycled materials for remanufacturing
	Establishment of "circularity" certification labels to verify the veracity of the company's circular-sustainable model, providing information on the production of the product and its management at the end of its useful life (e.g. percentages of recycled material and original raw material used in its manufacture, percentages of waste that goes to landfill and is reused at the end of its useful life, etc.)

A clear example of the last of the actions indicated in the furniture sector is the “Furniture Product Circularity” label developed by the Italian technological centre COSMOB:

INPUT INDICATORS

Characteristics of each component

<p>DEFINITION OF PRODUCT COMPONENTS</p>	<p>Single components characterizing the product (es: BASE, SHELF, CABINET, DOOR, FOOT, HARDWARE, etc.)</p>
<p>IDENTIFICATION OF MATERIALS for each COMPONENT</p>	<p>Types of materials of which the component is composed: - SHELF = wood-based panel - LEGS = plastic - HANDLE = metal + plastic.</p>
<p>WEIGHT UNIT Kg</p>	<p>Weight (Kg) of each single component.</p>

Characteristics of the materials for each component

WHAT?	
<p>% RAW MATERIAL</p>	<p>Amount of material that has no recycled content.</p>
<p>% RECYCLED</p>	<p>Amount of material that has recycled, pre and post-consumer content.</p>
<p>% SUB-PRODUCT</p>	<p>Secondary product derived from a production process.</p>
<p>% FROM RENEWABLE SOURCE</p>	<p>Material able to regenerate over time, from animal or plant origin.</p>
<p>% FROM NON-RENEWABLE SOURCE</p>	<p>Material that is unable to regenerate over time.</p>
HOW?	
<p>CERTIFICATION</p>	<p>Independent third party certifications or suppliers declarations.</p>

OUTPUT INDICATORS

Production waste

WHAT?

% RECYCLING | % of the weight of the recycled material.

% LANDFILL | % of the weight of landfill material.

% ENERGY VALORIZATION | % of the weight of the material for energy valorization.

% COMPOST | % of the weight of the compost material.

HOW?

LAW DECREES | D.Lgs 152/2006 and DPCM 23 Dic 2020 Unified Environmental Declaration Form (MUD) and the Waste Identification Form (FIR).

INPUT SCARTI DI PRODUZIONE SPECIFICI	
COMPONENTE PRODOTTO	MATERIALE
Residui di taglio - pannello base legno	legno
Imballaggi mix - Viti, bulloni e accessori	plastica
...	...

OUTPUT - SCARTI DI PRODUZIONE				
RICICLO %	DISCARICATO %	VALORIZZAZIONE ENERGETICA %	COMPOST %	Riferimenti informazioni
100%	0%	0%	0%	MUD
0%	100%	0%	0%	MUD
...
...
...

Disassembly

WHAT?

IDENTIFICATION OF COMPONENTS TO DISPOSE | Technical analysis of the product features to identify every potential disassemblable components.

HOW?

LAW DECREE | Par. 3.2.11 of DM 11st January 2017, CAM Furniture of the Ministry of the Environment.

INPUT PRODUZIONE SPECIFICHE PRODOTTO		
COMPONENTE PRODOTTO	MATERIALE	DISASSEMBLAGGIO DEL COMPONENTE DAL PRODOTTO %
Piedino	Plastica - ABS	100%

Final destination

The **indicators shall be assessed** for each component:

WHAT?

- % RECYCLING** | % of the weight of the recycled material.
- % LANDFILL** | % of the weight of landfill material.
- % ENERGETIC RECOVERY** | % of the weight of the material intended for energy enhancement.
- % COMPOST** | % of the weight of the compost material.

HOW?

STATISTICAL PROCESSING | COSMOB R&D Area; statistical processing on national and international sources:

- "Rapporto Rifiuti Urbani - ISPRA"
- "Rapporto Rifiuti Speciali - ISPRA"
- "Catasto dei rifiuti ISPRA"
- "Rapporto l'Italia del Riciclo, - Fondazione per lo Sviluppo Sostenibile" and "FISE UNICIRCULAR"
- "Statistiche sui rifiuti UE - Eurostat"

Material Circularity Index

This rate is calculated on the basis of the approach defined by the Ellen McArthur Foundation:

$$MCI = 1 - LCI * F(x)$$

Sector	Regulatory incentives/actions
Construction	Legislation to make the "polluter pays" principle a reality
	Promote <i>ecodesign</i> in the phases prior to product development to facilitate disassembly, establishing coding standards and reverse logistics to improve the flow of recycled materials for remanufacturing

4.2 Fiscal incentives

This category includes fiscal incentive such as taxation, subsidies, financing, and internalising the cost of externalities.

The European Commission (2019) report on accelerating the transition to the circular economy have identified areas where incentives would be needed:

- Level playing field incentives that enable circular business to have a better chance to compete and succeed in the market
- Value chain collaboration incentives to enable and reward collaboration to optimise circular economy solutions
- Long-term value creation incentives to reward product longevity models
- Market participation incentives to engage end-users in the value chain to ensure circularity of products and material
- Integration of public good incentives to take into account the cost of negative externalities and the benefits of positive externalities
- Finance knowledge build-up incentives to increase the understanding of financing circular business models
- First mover's action incentives to create market demand and engage consumers in circular business models

Stimulating a level playing field between different business models and raw versus secondary/recycled resources and materials may require further fiscal policy instruments. These include material and resource taxes. Environmental tax can be implemented at different stages of the value chain:

- At the extraction stage
- At the input of the material to its first industrial use
- At the final consumption of products including the material.

Incentives for financing circular business models would be needed. Finance providers should be able to understand the financial and operational risks, as well as the residual value after a product's first life. Specifically, internalising externalities is an area where fiscal incentives can play a role. One example is related to greater transparency in the food value chain.

Likewise, the following tables show the main initiative identified by the participants in the demonstrators in the three sectors:

Sector	Fiscal incentives/actions
	Reconfiguring the R&D deduction in consideration of the circular economy

Automotive / Furniture / Construction	Improve the taxation of remanufactured products, for example with reduced VAT for these labour-intensive products with low CO2 emissions that generate local wealth
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Conclusions

The circular economy conveys the idea that it is possible to generate economic activity that not only does not destroy the planet, but also helps to regenerate it. In this transition of models, a cross-cutting element to work on is R&D&I, where taxation is vital: the change of model should make use of environmental taxation, considering it to be one of the main economic instruments for the protection of the environment. It is also considered as a great ally on which to rely, as taxation is a source of incentives for changes in the behaviour of producers and consumers towards less waste generation, as well as a permanent incentive towards more respectful behaviour - since, if behaviour is modified, the tax burden decreases - and towards innovation - new forms of production, transport and consumption. It also puts the "polluter pays" principle into practice.

In short, and although the legislator is reluctant to introduce tax incentives because of the problems of control that they entail, several tax proposals are being put forward, it is necessary to reflect on the approach to taxation, which should be oriented towards unsustainable resources (thus, taxation acting as a revulsive for them), and at the same time alleviating or eliminating the burden of renewable resources (conservation/environmental sustainability). It cannot be forgotten that environmental taxation has a fundamental role to play in the transition towards a circular economy.

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